

Local Government in Moldova

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe
with the support of the Congress of Local Authorities of Moldova (CALM)

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Moldova: An Introduction

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Intergovernmental relations in Moldova are regulated according to the Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration. According to Article 6 of this law, the local and district councils, mayors and district presidents are autonomous administrative authorities, solving the public affairs of villages (communes), cities (municipalities) and districts. The relations between the central and local public authorities are based on the principles of autonomy, legality, transparency and collaboration in solving common problems. There is no relation of subordination between the central and local authorities, and between the first level and the second level public authorities, except for the cases provided by law. Any administrative control exercised over the activity carried out by the local public authorities must not pursue another purpose than ensuring the observance of legality and of constitutional principles, and the control of opportunity may aim only at achieving the competences delegated to local public authorities (LPAs), under the law. The central public administration authorities consult the representative associations of the LPA authorities in the issues related to the local public administration.

The principle of consultation on the issues related to the local public administration is an important reference in the intergovernmental relations in Moldova. This principle is stated also by the Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization that refers to the principle of institutional dialogue, as a situation which involves informing and consulting, in due time, local public authorities, in the planning and decision-making process, through their associative structures, on any issues that concern them directly or are related to the process of administrative decentralization.

To facilitate intergovernmental dialogue and consultations, the Law on Administrative Decentralization prescribed the creation of the Joint Decentralization Commission. Such a parity commission in the area of decentralization with the participation of the representatives of LPA associations was created in 2008.¹⁵ The Commission is composed of representatives of the national and local governments, to ensure communication and institutionalized dialogue between the central government and LPAs. Nevertheless, for a long time, the lack of a unified voice of local authorities has negatively influenced advocacy for local government reforms.

¹⁵ Government Decree no 93/2008, substituted by the Government Decree no 608/2010.

The Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova (CALM) plays a fundamental role in intergovernmental relations in Moldova. CALM was constituted in March 2010,¹⁶ by territorial administrative units organized under the law as towns and villages and by their professional associations. This level of membership provides both capacity and political consolidation. Nowadays CALM is the largest and most representative association of local authorities in Moldova. It provides legal advice and supports local autonomy and decentralization. CALM represents 800 LPAs as members with full rights out of the 898 existing in Moldova. Even after the establishment of CALM, it took many years before the voice of local authorities became sufficiently important, heard and taken into account by central authorities.

Despite CALM being an active player in the area of decentralization and having now a high degree of representability of first level LPAs, dialog and intergovernmental relations between local and the central governments remains challenging. Due to political instability and the lack of political commitment to advance reforms, the Joint Decentralization Commission has not been able to serve as a successful platform for intergovernmental relations. Following an opinion expressed by CALM, '[u]nfortunately, all communication, consultation and dialogue between LPA/CALM and the government has disappeared. And the current legal format of communication and dialogue between central and local authorities has proven to be non-functional, selective and formal.'¹⁷ Recent Post-monitoring assessments developed by the Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe enforced this ascertainment, stating that '[o]f special concern was the fact that no appropriate consultation mechanisms could be identified between central government and local authorities.'

During 2017, in spite of the fact that this was a decisive year for the implementation of the Decentralization Strategy and other commitments in the field of decentralization and strengthening local autonomy, the Joint Decentralization Commission has not convened at all. Intergovernmental relations over the past three years continued to be formal, with central authorities preferring to unilaterally promote their political vision, through the development of the legislation without proper consideration of the interests of the LPAs, in the areas that target also the interests of the local communities.

Overall, intergovernmental consultation mechanisms are not sufficiently institutionalized and consolidated in Moldova. However, some progress in the institutionalized dialogue between CALM and the government is observed. CALM obtained the right to attend the weekly meetings of the Government Cabinet and the meetings of the Committee of General Secretaries of the Government (the structure which initially examines the draft normative acts before their approval by the government). Similarly, dialogue with parliamentary commissions

¹⁶ 'About us' (*Congress of Local Authorities from Moldova*, last updated 2021) <<https://www.calm.md/despre-noi/>>.

¹⁷ 'Congresul Autorităților Locale, extrem de îngrijorat de starea democrației locale' (*Stiri MD*, 1 December 2017) <<https://stiri.md/article/social/congresul-autoritatilor-locale-extrem-de-ingrijorat-de-starea-democratiei-locale>>.

has been consolidated and institutional dialogue with ministries and public agencies has been established.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 435/2006 on Administrative Decentralization

Law no 436/2006 on Local Public Administration

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe, 'Post-Monitoring Report on the Republic of Moldova' (2020)

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